

Nano Ca(OH)₂ synthesis using a cost-effective and innovative method: reactivity study

Giuliana Taglieri^a, Valeria Daniele^{a*}, Ludovico Macera^a, Claudia Mondelli^b

^a *Department of Industrial and Information Engineering and Economics, University of L'Aquila, Piazzale E. Pontieri 1, 67100, Monteluco di Roio, Roio Poggio, L'Aquila (AQ), Italy*

^b *CNR-IOM, Institut Laue-Langevin, 38042 Grenoble Cedex 9, France*

Abstract

Ca(OH)₂ nanoparticles in hydro-alcoholic dispersion (*nanolime*) are currently used for eco-compatible treatments of carbonate-based substrates in the field of Cultural Heritage conservation. Unfortunately, at present nanolime is synthesized by processes which present some drawbacks (considerable cost, multiple steps, low specific production yield), thus limiting the potential of its applications. We have developed a single-step procedure, based on an ion exchange process, making it possible to produce pure and crystalline Ca(OH)₂ nanoparticles easily in water, at room temperature and ambient pressure, starting from cheap or renewable reactants. The simplicity of the process and its time- and energy-saving aspects are very promising factors for extending the production from lab to industrial scale. The aim of this paper is to investigate the structural and morphological features of the nanoparticles produced and to analyze the influence of crucial parameters of the synthesis process (i.e. time, water usage, reagent concentration and reaction volume) on the nanoparticles' characteristics. The nanolime produced is investigated by XRD, FTIR, TEM and AFM techniques. The nanoparticle reactivity in the carbonation process is also investigated, by varying the suspension concentration, the solvent and relative humidity conditions. Pure, crystalline and very reactive Ca(OH)₂ nanoparticles are obtained. The nanoparticles are constituted of thin lamellas, composed of primary hexagonal nanoparticles <10nm, irrespective of time, water employed, reagents concentration and reaction volume.

Keywords: Nanoparticle synthesis, Lime, Carbonation, X-ray diffraction, Electron transmission microscopy, AFM

1. Introduction

Calcium hydroxide, (Ca(OH)₂, portlandite), is an important compound used in a variety of industrial, chemical, and environmental applications.¹⁻² Furthermore, it is one of the most ancient and widely used building materials, being traditionally used as a binder or a primary material in architecture and decorative arts.³ In the field of heritage conservation, Ca(OH)₂ can be considered one of the best candidate in terms of compatibility for consolidating

decayed carbonate stones⁴⁻⁶, mural paintings⁷⁻⁸, and all carbonatic-based decorative and architectural surfaces.⁹ This is due to the well-known carbonation process that occurs when $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is exposed to atmospheric carbon dioxide in damp conditions.¹⁰ However, the carbonation is generally incomplete and mainly depends on the physical properties of portlandite (particle size and surface area) and on relative humidity, pH and degree of supersaturation.¹¹⁻¹³ Roman historical sources, such as Plinius and Vitruvius, indicated that the slaked lime quality was enhanced by storage in pure water.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ It has been found that, when aging in water, the crystal morphology and size of calcium hydroxide particles undergo significant changes from typical prismatic crystal aspect to sub-micrometer plate-like crystals, deriving from a secondary nucleation of plate-like nano-sized $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ The higher surface area and the changes in morphology can explain the greater water adsorption capability and the resulting greater plasticity, water retention and workability of mortars prepared by aged lime putty. The reduction of particle dimensions to a sub-micrometric scale can also lead to higher reactivity, such as the faster carbonation process of mortars prepared by aged lime putty compared to mortars containing commercially available, hydrated lime.¹¹ However, prolonged storage in water usually takes several months or even years.¹⁸

Currently, typical procedures adopted to prepare sub-micrometric (or nano-sized) and plate-like $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles consist of wet chemical methods, carried out at high temperature and/or at high pressure, in aqueous, alcohol or organic solvents.¹⁹⁻²³ Moreover, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is rarely the only product of the reaction, requiring time-consuming purification. Purification is also needed to eliminate the organic compounds, used in the synthesis medium, requiring accurate procedures because of the adsorption on the nanoparticle surfaces, and leading to higher costs and low-yield synthesis.²⁴ The development of versatile, cost-effective and scalable methods of achieving predictable nanoparticle properties is therefore paramount for the successful introduction of these materials for widespread use.

Recently, we patented an original and innovative single-step process making it possible to produce pure nano-sized $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles (nCH) and overcoming the limitations of current procedures.^{25, 26} The method employs cheap and renewable reactants, operates at room temperature, does not require intermediate steps to eliminate undesired compounds (e.g. washing/peptization), and drastically reduces synthesis times. The nCH is produced in only 60 minutes by an ion-exchange process between an anionic exchange resin (R-OH) placed in contact with an aqueous solution of calcium chloride. The substitution of -OH groups on the resin substrate with the Cl^- ions in solution leads, in conditions of supersaturation, to the formation of pure, crystalline and reactive nCH with no secondary phase.

Moreover, as the exchange process is reversible, it is possible to regenerate resin and to reuse it for a new synthesis operation, leading to a cyclic procedure suitable for scaled-up production.

The aim of this work is to study the main features of the nanoparticles produced by varying certain critical parameters of the synthesis route, such as time, water usage, concentration of the initial reagents and volume of reaction. The nanoparticles produced are characterized by structural, spectroscopic, and morphological techniques, such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and atomic force microscopy (AFM). Moreover, we investigated the kinetic stability of the nanoparticle suspension produced and the reactivity of the nanoparticles in relation to the carbonation process in air. For this purpose, we considered the influence of several factors, such as solvent (water or water/alcohol mixtures), suspension concentration, and relative humidity conditions (simulating normal, intermediate and high moisture conditions).

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Materials

Analytical reagent-grade calcium chloride, (CaCl_2 , Merck); ion-exchange resin (Dowex Monosphere 550A, Sigma-Aldrich), in the form of translucent spherical beads characterized by a particle size equal to $590 \pm 50 \mu\text{m}$; 2-propanol (>99.8 %, Sigma Aldrich); deionized water **W1** (specific conductivity= $1 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$); tap water **W2** (specific conductivity $250 \text{mS}/\text{cm}$). In Table I, the composition of the tap water (analyzed by HPLC, Dionex-Dx120) was reported.

2.2 Process of production of calcium hydroxide nanoparticles

nCH production was performed, at room temperature by pouring a 0.1 M calcium chloride (CaCl_2) aqueous solution with a proper resin amount and maintaining the preparation under moderate stirring. Two different reaction times (τ) were considered: 60 and 15 minutes, respectively. Afterwards, the white precipitate phase that formed was separated from the resin particles by a simple sieving procedure. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ production was regulated by the following reaction:

occurring around each resin particle, homogeneously diffused throughout the volume of the solution. Two suspensions were obtained, named **S60_{0.1W1}** and **S15_{0.1W1}**, each characterized by a nominal $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ concentration of 10 g/l. Following the same procedure, a suspension **S15_{0.1W2}** was prepared by using tap water **W2** in place of deionized water (**W1**), for $\tau = 15$ minutes.

Moreover, to analyze the reproducibility of the nanoparticle's features, in terms of phase composition and reactivity for larger productions, we increased by an order of magnitude the concentration of the reagents, using both deionized and tap water. After 15 minutes, the samples obtained were named **S15_{1W1}** and **S15_{1W2}** respectively. The procedure was extended to larger volumes of reaction, an order of magnitude bigger; for this task, only tap water was considered and the sample obtained was named **S15_{1*W2}**.

For all the suspensions, the kinetics of the ion exchange process, in terms of chloride concentration (CC), were monitored. Samples were homogeneously taken from each suspension at different times, from the beginning until the end of the process; the CC values were measured by means of an ion-sensitive electrode (Metrohm).

The yield of the production (Y) was also evaluated. It was defined as the percentage of the experimental dry residual content measured from each suspension (CH_{meas}) with respect to the stoichiometric $Ca(OH)_2$ values evaluated by means of reaction (1) (CH_{stoic}):

$$Y = \frac{CH_{meas}}{CH_{stoic}} * 100$$

In particular, CH_{meas} was measured by taking 15 samples from each suspension, which were immersed in 2-propanol to avoid the carbonation process, and dried in an oven at 110°C: the average value was considered.

2.3 Characterization of calcium hydroxide nanoparticles

The phase composition and crystallite size/strain of the synthesized particles were determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) on a PANalytical X'PertPRO diffractometer equipped with a Ni filter (CuK_{α} radiation), in the 5-80°2 θ exploration range. The diffraction patterns were collected using a solid-state detector (PIXcel, PANalytical), with the detected X-ray photons binned into constant steps of 0.013°2 θ (time per step 1600s). In particular, we investigated:

- a) the particles directly in suspension. Specifically, samples were analyzed by means of 1 mm diameter glass capillaries, considering aqueous dispersions (100% water) and alcoholic dispersions (obtained by substituting 90% of the water volume with an equivalent volume of 2-propanol). Acquisition of blank contribution (i.e. measures of pure water and of hydro-alcoholic solution) was also measured;
- b) the dried powders, obtained after drying the suspension in an oven at 110°C. The following drying procedure was considered: a homogeneous sample was taken from suspension (previously maintained in an ultrasonic bath for 15'), immersed in alcohol to avoid the carbonation process, and then dried in an oven.

XRD patterns were elaborated using a Profile Fit software (HighScorePlus software package, PANalytical), and crystalline phases were attributed by ICDD and ICSD reference databases. XRD peak broadening analysis (by means of the Debye–Scherrer formula and the Williamson-Hall method²⁷⁻²⁸) were performed to evaluate the average crystallite size, D_{hkl} (i.e. the size of the coherent diffraction domains), and lattice strain, ϵ , of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals. When evaluated by means of the Williamson-Hall method, the average crystallite size was indicated as $\langle D \rangle$.

The Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements were performed by a NexusTM 870 FT-IR (ThermoNicolet, USA) spectrophotometer, over a range of 400 - 4000 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The FTIR spectra of thin pellets of nanoparticles, in the form of oven-dried powder, in a KBr matrix were analyzed. In particular, in order to avoid the carbonation process, the drying procedure was carried out by immersing the sample in alcohol and then drying it in oven at 100°C.

The nanoparticle morphology and dimensions were observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, model Philips CM100, 100 KV); by using ImageJ software, the particle size was also evaluated. High-resolution TEM (HRTEM, model Tecnai 12, G2 Twin, 120 KV, FEI) was also performed, in conjunction with electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS). TEM samples were prepared in a glove box under nitrogen atmosphere, to avoid carbonation.

AFM measurements were performed by a *Cypher Asylum Research* instrument using a cantilever Bruker model SNL 10 in tapping mode: some drops of the diluted suspension were dispersed, under nitrogen atmosphere, on flat surfaces of a single-crystal silicon. In order to avoid carbonation, the samples were maintained under nitrogen atmosphere for 24 hours until solvent evaporation was finished.

2.4 Kinetic stability measurements

In order to investigate the kinetic stability of the suspensions produced, partial substitution of water as a dispersing medium was performed. In fact, as reported in the literature, nCH aqueous suspensions are not stable in time, because of their tendency to aggregate in the presence of water. Stable dispersions were achieved by substituting water with short-chain alcohols, such as 2-propanol, which demonstrated the good de-aggregation and stabilization ability of the nanoparticles.²⁴ Here, we investigated the best conditions for the stability of the suspensions produced, by varying both the 2-propanol /water ratio (A/W) and the suspension concentration. Starting from the aqueous suspensions **S60**_{0.1W1}, **S15**_{0.1W1} and **S15**_{0.1W2}, we performed the following 2-propanol volume substitutions: 25% (**S60**_{0.1W1_25}, **S15**_{0.1W1_25} and **S15**_{0.1W2_25}); 50% (**S60**_{0.1W1_50}, and **S15**_{0.1W1_50} and **S15**_{0.1W2_50}); and 90% (**S60**_{0.1W1_90}, and **S15**_{0.1W1_90} and **S15**_{0.1W2_90}). For each sample, the absorbance A was measured at $\lambda=600\text{nm}$ as a function of time t ,

for up to 120 hours, (Lambda 25 Perkin-Elmer ultraviolet/visible spectrophotometer). The relative kinetic stability of the dispersions was determined as the ξ -parameter.³⁰⁻³¹ The dispersions, placed in an ultrasonic bath before analysis, were analyzed both at a concentration of 10g/l and of 5g/l.

2.5 Analysis of the carbonation process

The carbonation process of the nCH produced was evaluated considering both aqueous and hydro-alcoholic dispersions, at 10g/l and different A/W ratios (25%, 50%, and 90%, respectively). The carbonation was monitored by exposing each nanolime suspension to air and evaporating it in ambient conditions ($T=20^{\circ}\text{C}$; relative humidity, $\text{RH}=45\pm 5\%$; $p\text{CO}_2 \approx 10^{-3.5}\text{atm}$, i.e. the standard concentration of CO_2 in ambient air). The nanolime reactivity at 5g/l (typical of commercial nanolimes) was also evaluated; A/W ratios of both 50% and 90% were considered here. For both the nanolime suspension concentrations, different RH values were considered, equal to $45\pm 5\%$, $75\pm 5\%$ and $95\pm 5\%$, respectively.

Three samples of 0.12ml were taken from each suspension, placed on a XRD zero-background sample holder and dried in a glass container at a temperature of $20\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and different RH settings. The container was not airtight to guarantee a small but continuous flow of air, thus allowing the carbonation process in similar CO_2 conditions. By varying the RH values, different evaporation times of solvents were observed. Actually, at $\text{RH} = 45\%$, the evaporation time was 45 minutes for aqueous suspensions, and 20 and 5 minutes for $\text{A/W}=50$ and $\text{A/W}=90$, respectively: at $\text{RH} = 90\%$, we observed 150 minutes in water and about 60 minutes for $\text{A/W}=90$. Each diffraction pattern was collected, on dried powders, in the angular range 15 to $50^{\circ}2\theta$, constant steps $0.026^{\circ}2\theta$, time per step 800s (PANalytical X'PertPRO diffractometer). The patterns were elaborated using the HighScorePlus software (PANalytical), and the crystalline phases were attributed by ICSD and ICDD reference databases. The ratio between the CaCO_3 Bragg peaks area and the area of the whole XRD pattern was assumed to be the carbonation process efficiency (χ), as previously reported.³⁴ The ratio between the areas under different CaCO_3 crystalline phases was also reported. These results were compared to those reported in the literature, evaluated from commercial nanoparticles exposed to similar conditions.^{13,32}

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Kinetics of the exchange process and production yield

The ion exchange process exhibited rapid kinetic, both for 0.1M and 1M aqueous solutions, showing a strong reduction of the CC values during the first 30 seconds (Figure 1). A CC saturation value < 0.2 g/l was then reached after 15 minutes. From the dry residual contents, Y values from 87% to 100% were obtained, irrespective of reaction time, water employed, reagent concentrations and water volume (Table II).

3.2 Characterization of the particles produced

The phase composition of the particles produced, analyzed directly in suspension, was reported in Figure 2, in relation to aqueous suspensions (samples **S60_{0.1W1}**, **S15_{0.1W1}** and **S15_{0.1W2}**) and to alcoholic suspensions (samples **S60_{0.1W1_90}**, **S15_{0.1W1_90}** and **S15_{0.1W2_90}**). The comparison with the ICSD reference database revealed that all the suspensions were constituted of only pure and crystalline $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, (ICSD reference pattern: portlandite, #98-020-2221). From blank measurements, the background signal was attributed to the pure water or to the 2-propanol/water contribution. As reported in Table III, for the **S60_{0.1W1}** sample a slightly higher value of $\langle D \rangle$ was obtained, while ϵ did not reveal crystal defects, irrespective of synthesis time and water employed. Moreover, the D_{hkl} values measured for each crystallographic plane revealed no marked differences, denoting equiaxed $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals.³³ Similar results were obtained for particles dispersed in alcoholic suspensions.

In contrast, dried $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles exhibited orientation effects along the $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction, as also observed in previous work^{19-21, 34} (Figure 3). Actually, as discussed in a previous paper¹⁷, during the drying procedure the nanosized $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals “*may assemble irreversibly via oriented (epitaxial) attachment*”, allowing interparticle structural continuity. In fact, the $\langle D \rangle$ measured from dried particles (see Table IV) were of an order of magnitude higher than what was observed in suspension, due to the formation of such polycrystalline-oriented aggregates.³⁵

FTIR investigation (Figure S1) showed a strong and sharp O-H stretching absorption band at 3640 cm^{-1} , and a H–O–H bending vibration at 1655 cm^{-1} due to the presence of the solid $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, was observed. The broad band centered at 3450 cm^{-1} was related to the O-H stretching modes of free-molecular- H_2O stretching^{12-13, 36}, but could be also ascribed to the presence of structural water within amorphous calcium carbonate (ACC).³⁷ The well-defined band at 850 cm^{-1} (ν_2 asymmetric CO_3 deformation), together with the broad band at 1460 cm^{-1} (ν_3 asymmetric CO_3 stretching), underlined the presence of CaCO_3 ^{24, 38}, which probably occurred during the drying procedure in the oven (carried out in air). Additional sharp bands were observed at 713 cm^{-1} and 1082 cm^{-1} , related to the ν_4 and ν_1 modes of CO_3 in calcite.²⁴ The doublet around 2800 cm^{-1} , corresponded to the C-H stretching of adsorbed alcohol or, more likely, a newly-formed Ca-alkoxide, due to the drying procedure in alcohol, as described in Section 2.3.²⁴

In Figure 4 TEM representative images of the particles present in samples **S15_{0.1W1}** and **S15_{0.1W2}** are shown. We observed very thin hexagonal lamellas, nearly transparent to the electron beam, preferentially aligned along the basal plane of the hexagon, with side dimensions generally < 200 nm; single nanoparticles, ≤ 10 nm, placed either on the surface and on the borders of the grid were also observed (Figure 4b)). From higher magnification images, each lamella appeared to be constituted of a self-assembly of primary nanoparticles (≤ 10 nm), strictly bonded along the borders and revealing an internal mesoporous structure (Figure 4c)). The presence of Moiré fringes in overlapping areas between two lamellas revealed the crystallinity of the primary nanoparticles. Moreover, the hexagonal lamella, placed in parallel to the electron beam, presented a thickness < 10 nm (Figure 4d)). Similar results were obtained for the **S60_{0.1W1}** sample. Regarding samples **S15_{1W1}** and **S15_{1W2}**, TEM images revealed the presence of both hexagonal but also irregularly shaped aggregates (Figures 5a-b)). These aggregates were characterized by a higher thickness compared to what had been previously observed, but were always composed of primary nanoparticles ≤ 10 nm (Figure 5b). Comparable images were obtained for the **S15_{1*W2}** sample (Figure S2). HRTEM analysis on the **S15_{1W1}** sample confirmed that the aggregates were composed of hexagonal primary nanoparticles, crystalline and ≤ 10 nm in size (Figure 6), as observed in a previous paper.³⁹ In particular, from EELS analysis (Figure S3)), the nanoparticles were constituted only of Ca and O, confirming that no carbonation had occurred during TEM sample preparation. The Selected Area Electron Diffraction (SAED) analysis confirmed the presence of a Ca(OH)₂ crystalline structure (inset of Figure 6).

AFM investigations on the samples **S15_{0.1W1}** and **S15_{1W1}** (Figures 7,8) confirmed the presence of primary nanoparticles with dimensions ≤ 10 nm, characterized by a thickness less than 7 nm and 2.5nm, respectively. Such investigations indicated that, by working at a high reagent concentration, primary nanoparticles with comparable purity and dimensions can be produced, but presenting a reduced thickness in keeping with an enhanced nucleation process, due to the higher supersaturation conditions.

3.3 Colloidal stability of Ca(OH)₂ suspensions

Measurements of relative kinetic stability of **S15_{0.1W1}** hydro-alcoholic suspensions (10g/l) showed that Ca(OH)₂ particles tended to settle rapidly, resulting in a sudden drop in absorbance during the first ten minutes, for all A/W ratios except for A/W=50% (see Figure 9). In fact, for A/W=50% the suspension presented a slight decrease in absorbance during the first 30 minutes, then remaining stable up to 240 minutes. Similar results were observed for the suspensions **S60_{0.1W1}** and **S15_{0.1W2}**. We were able to relate these results to the presence of water inside the

Ca(OH)₂ suspensions; in fact, water which remained inside the preparation ($\geq 10\%$), can limit the disaggregating effect of the pure alcohol solvent, as observed in the literature.^{24, 34, 40} However, the ability of the A/W = 50% mixture to reach optimum conditions in terms of stability can be related to its higher viscosity compared to the others, as shown in the literature.^{41, 42}

3.4 Analyses of the carbonation process

There are at least six different phases of CaCO₃: three anhydrous crystalline polymorphs (calcite, aragonite, and vaterite), two hydrated crystalline forms called monohydrocalcite (CaCO₃·H₂O, ikaite (CaCO₃·6H₂O) and amorphous CaCO₃ (ACC).⁴³⁻⁴⁴ Intermediate stages of CaCO₃ hydrates are also recognizable, such as calcium carbonate hydroxide hydrate (Ca₃(CO₃)₂(OH)₂·1.5H₂O, called CCH).⁴⁵ The carbonation process of nanolime can be affected by the physical properties of portlandite crystals (particle size and surface area)^{12, 46}, as well as by the type of solvent and concentration⁴⁷⁻⁴⁸, and by environmental conditions.^{12, 24, 32} In this sense, the carbonation process can be considered an important means of investigation not only to provide useful information for the application of nanolime, but also because it can offer indirect indications on both particle dimensions and aggregates, whose presence could be related to the solvent and the suspension concentration.

XRD analyses of the nanolime suspensions at 10g/l, exposed to RH = 45%, were shown in Figure 10. Both the aqueous and the A/W=25% samples presented a complete transformation of nanolime into CaCO₃, in the form of calcite. When the alcohol content was increased, the carbonation process slowed down, also due to the faster evaporation rate of solvents (5 minutes in the most alcoholic suspension), denoting the detrimental role of alcohol. However, an intermediate behavior was found for A/W=50%, giving values of χ of 86±5%, 81±7% and 82±5% for **S60_{0.1W1}**, **S15_{0.1W1}** and **S15_{0.1W2}**, respectively. In particular, calcite was observed as the main phase, together with small amounts of CCH (ICDD pattern #00-023-0107). The presence of CCH confirmed what was reported in a previous paper⁴⁵, namely that the carbonate formation from Ca(OH)₂ could proceed by intermediate steps, where CO₂ molecules were introduced with water which, in turn, was gradually lost until pure calcite was obtained.

In Table V we summarized the results obtained from A/W=50% and A/W=90% samples, at different RH conditions, and at concentrations of 10g/l and 5g/l. The fundamental role of water appeared evident, either as a dispersing medium or as affecting the amount of moisture in the air. In particular, all the samples having A/W =50% showed almost complete carbonation in pure calcite (even when at low RH conditions), also in relation to the slow solvent evaporation times. When A/W=90% was considered, the samples showed a poorer carbonation ability, but only at a

concentration of 10g/l and at low RH condition. The carbonation ability increased for suspension concentration of 5g/l, with yield values ranging from $45\pm 11\%$ to $61\pm 34\%$ (RH=45%), up to 100% (RH=95%), with a pure calcite phase formation. Moreover, the samples with A/W=90% revealed the highest variability in the results - resulting in a higher uncertainty - with respect to all the samples with A/W=50%. This fact can be related to the ability of the latter ratio to stabilize the suspension (as observed in Figure 9), giving the best disagglomeration of the nanoparticles, therefore guaranteeing a reproducible sampling and also a higher reactivity.

Regarding the reactivity of the suspensions **S15_{1W1}** and **S15_{1W2}** (reported in Table VI), the samples with A/W = 50% showed almost, if not complete, carbonation in the form of calcite for all RH conditions, as similarly observed with low reagent concentrations. In contrast, at A/W = 90% a reduction in χ values was observed, probably related both to the faster evaporation rate of the solvent and to the smaller nanoparticle thickness (see Figure 8), resulting in denser and less reactive agglomerates in the alcoholic medium. In order to verify this hypothesis, we left the alcoholic samples for 15 minutes in an ultrasonic bath, before exposing them to air for carbonation. The results obtained showed that, for $RH \geq 75\%$, χ values increased up to 100%.

If compared with literature results,^{24, 32, 49-52} all our suspensions appeared to be characterized by a higher reactivity. In fact, in the cited works, at $RH \leq 54\%$, $Ca(OH)_2$ remained essentially untransformed for 7 days^{32, 50} and the carbonation process was only completed after 28 days. At higher RH conditions (75% and 90%), our nanolime presented a yield essentially ranging between 90 and 100% after 5 minutes of exposure to air, whereas in other literature works $Ca(OH)_2$ remained the unique phase even after 2-4 hours⁵² and the carbonation process was completed only after 7 days.^{32, 51} Moreover, in the cited works, calcite was never the only phase that formed, with vaterite, aragonite and monohydrocalcite also being observed, depending on the RH conditions. The transformation of calcium hydroxide into calcite, as a unique and pure phase, is of fundamental importance in the applicative fields, because calcite guarantees perfect compatibility, from a structural and morphological point of view, with all carbonatic substrates.

Conclusions

$Ca(OH)_2$ nanoparticles were prepared using a straightforward and single-step method, starting with inexpensive or renewable reagents and working in aqueous media at ambient pressure and room temperature. The $Ca(OH)_2$ nanoparticles were pure and crystalline, irrespective of time, water employed, reagent concentration and volume of reaction. By TEM, the dried nanoparticles appeared to be constituted of thin hexagonal lamellas, composed of

primary nanoparticles < 10nm in length and 6nm in thickness. In addition, the nanoparticles - both for the A/W=90% but especially in the A/W=50% samples - showed a high reactivity in terms of the carbonation process, resulting in a transformation into pure calcite in only a few hours, under normal to high values for moisture conditions. Moreover, the scaled-up production, performed by varying the concentration of the initial reagents as well as the volume of reaction, showed that the nanoparticles remained essentially unchanged in terms of morphology and reactivity. As a consequence, the method's features and the time- and energy-saving aspects make the possibility of scaling up the production from lab to industrial level a very promising prospect.

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Figures caption list

Figure 1. Percentage of chlorides in solution, at different times during the exchange process, relative to aqueous suspensions at different CaCl_2 concentrations, with deionized water (*W1*) and tap water (*W2*): (a)-(c) 0.1M; (b)-(d) 1M.

Figure 2. XRD patterns of the nanolime dispersions: (a) particles dispersed in aqueous medium; (b) particles dispersed in hydro-alcoholic medium (10% water, 90% 2-propanol). Main Bragg peaks of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (portlandite, ICSD reference pattern #98-020-2221) were shown, with diffraction peaks labeled with hkl indices.

Figure 3. XRD patterns of dried powders from nanolime dispersions (oven temperature: 110°C). Main Bragg peaks of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (portlandite, ICSD reference pattern #98-020-2221) were labeled with hkl indices.

Figure 4. TEM images of nanoparticles present in suspensions **S15_{0.1W1}** and **S15_{0.1W2}**: (a) hexagonal and very thin lamellas, parallel or perpendicular to the electron beam; (b) image of a hexagonal lamella and single nanoparticles < 20nm dispersed on the grid; (c) mesoporous structure of lamella, composed of primary nanoparticles of about 10 nm; (d) a lamella, parallel to the electron beam, showing a thickness < 10 nm.

Figure 5. TEM images of sample **S15_{1W1}**, at different magnifications, of (a) a hexagonal lamella and (b) an aggregate of nanoparticles, both revealing a mesoporous structure.

Figure 6. HRTEM image and Selected Area Electron Diffraction (SAED) of sample **S15_{1W1}**.

Figure 7. AFM images of suspension **S15_{0.1W1}**: (a) single primary nanoparticles with dimensions ≤ 10 nm; (b) the corresponding elaborated profile along the Z-axis, showing a thickness < 7 nm.

Figure 8. AFM images of sample **S15_{1W1}**: (a) single primary nanoparticles with dimensions ≤ 10 nm; (b) the elaborated profile along the Z-axis, showing a thickness < 2.5nm.

Figure 9. Colloidal stability, in terms of the variation of absorbance (ξ) versus time, (at $\lambda=600$ nm), of suspension **S15_{0.1W1}** (concentration: 10g/l).

Figure 10. XRD patterns of the nanolime suspensions (10g/l), exposed for 1 hour in ambient conditions ($T=20^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH}=45\pm 5\%$). The different suspensions, relating to the A/W ratios were reported; (a) **S15_{0.1W1}**; (b) **S15_{0.1W2}**; (c) **S60_{0.1W1}**. (Key: *: portlandite #98-020-2221; °: calcite #98-002-0179; +: calcium carbonate hydroxide hydrate #00-023-0107).

Tables

Table I. Analysis of tap water W2 used here to produce Ca(OH)₂ nanoparticles.

pH	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at 20 °C)	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/L)	Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	Na ⁺ (mg/L)	K ⁺ (mg/L)	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	Total hardness (°F)
7.83	255	1.38	<0.05	40.80	1.52	0.86	0.42	1.04	2.72	127	10.84

Table II. Production yield (Y) of Ca(OH)₂ nanoparticles, by varying the reagent concentrations and the volume of water.

Sample	CaCl ₂ aqueous solution	Volume of water (ml)	CH _{stoic} (g)	CH _{meas} (g)	Y(%)
S60 _{0.1W1}	0.1M		3.32	3.3±0.3	99
S15 _{0.1W1}	0.1M		3.32	3.4±0.3	100
S15 _{1W1}	1M	400	33.2	29±3	87
S15 _{0.1W2}	0.1M		3.32	2.9±0.3	87
S15 _{1W2}	1M		33.2	32±3	96
S15 _{1*W2}	1M	4000	330	300±20	91

Table III. XRD results of Ca(OH)₂ nanoparticles in aqueous suspension

ICSD #98-020-2221			S60 _{0.1W1}					S15 _{0.1W1}			S15 _{0.1W2}				
<i>hkl</i>	<i>2θ</i> (°)	<i>I</i> (%)	<i>d</i> (Å)	<i>I</i> (%)	D _{hkl} (nm)	<D> (nm)	ε (%)	<i>I</i> (%)	D _{hkl} (nm)	<D> (nm)	ε (%)	<i>I</i> (%)	D _{hkl} (nm)	<D> (nm)	ε (%)
<i>001</i>	<i>18.086</i>	<i>64.0</i>	<i>4.90100</i>	64.9	54			59.8	35			65.1	38		
<i>010</i>	<i>28.723</i>	<i>9.3</i>	<i>3.10557</i>	9.4	51			9.1	39			9.4	40		
<i>011</i>	<i>34.152</i>	<i>100.0</i>	<i>2.62326</i>	100.0	51	41 ± 3	0.05	100.0	40	32 ± 1	0.05	100.0	40	33 ± 2	0.07
<i>012</i>	<i>47.209</i>	<i>24.0</i>	<i>1.92374</i>	24.1	55			26.1	45			23.9	42		
<i>110</i>	<i>50.886</i>	<i>29.7</i>	<i>1.79300</i>	29.2	55			32.5	46			28.9	42		
<i>111</i>	<i>54.447</i>	<i>16.3</i>	<i>1.68385</i>	16.1	56			18.4	49			15.9	43		

Data were corrected by instrumental broadening and compared to the Bragg peaks of Ca(OH)₂ ICSD reference pattern (portlandite, #98-020-2221), reported in italics.

Table IV. XRD results of Ca(OH)₂ dried nanoparticles

S60 _{0.1W1}					S15 _{0.1W1}			S15 _{0.1W2}				
<i>hkl</i>	<i>I</i> (%)	D _{hkl} (nm)	<D> (nm)	ε (%)	<i>I</i> (%)	D _{hkl} (nm)	<D> (nm)	ε (%)	<i>I</i> (%)	D _{hkl} (nm)	<D> (nm)	ε (%)
<i>001</i>	100.0	103			100.0	212			100.0	212		
<i>010</i>	28.0	204			17.0	204			31.0	103		
<i>011</i>	40.3	72	70 ± 5	0.10	28.4	72	105 ± 15	0.08	13.6	72	90 ± 10	0.04
<i>012</i>	7.6	216			6.2	216			2.1	59		
<i>110</i>	13.7	3089			8.1	3090			6.9	3086		
<i>111</i>	4.3	232			2.3	232			1.3	232		

Data were corrected by instrumental broadening.

Table V. Measurements of the carbonation yield (χ) and the CaCO₃ crystalline phases, in relation to different suspension concentrations, A/W ratios and relative humidity (RH) conditions

Sample	Suspension concentration (g/l)	A/W ratio (%)	RH 45±5%		RH 75±5%		RH 95±5%	
			CaCO ₃ crystalline phases	χ (%)	CaCO ₃ crystalline phases	χ (%)	CaCO ₃ crystalline phases	χ (%)
S60 _{0.1W1}	10	50	50% C 36% CCH	86±5	100% C	100	100% C	100
		90	45% C	42±2	100% C	92±14		
	5	50	83% C 17% CCH	100	100% C	100	100% C	100
		90	44% C 17% CCH	61±34	100% C	100		
S15 _{0.1W1}	10	50	43% C 38% CCH	81±7	97% C 3% CCH	100	100% C	100
		90	14% C 8% CCH	28±6	29% C 23% CCH	52±13		
	5	50	79% C 15% CCH	94±6	100% C	100	100% C	100
		90	9% Calcite 36% CCH	45±11	48% C 15% CCH	60±12		
S15 _{0.1W2}	10	50	33% C 49% CCH	82±5	100% C	100	100% C	100
		90	21% C 32% CCH	53±2	21% C 45% CCH	66±3		
	5	50	81% C 19% CCH	90±5	100% C	100	100% C	100
		90	20% C 34% CCH	54±20	79% C 12% CCH	91±15		

Exposure time: 1 hour; T=20°C

C = Calcite (CaCO₃) (ICSD #98-002-0179)

CCH = calcium carbonate hydroxide hydrate (Ca₃(CO₃)₂(OH)₂·1.5H₂O) (ICDD #00-023-0107)

Table VI. Measurements of the carbonation yield (χ) and the CaCO₃ crystalline phases: suspension obtained with the highest concentration of the initial reagent.

Sample	Suspension concentration (g/l)	A/W ratio (%)	RH 45±5%		RH 75±5%		RH 95±5%	
			CaCO ₃ crystalline phases	χ (%)	CaCO ₃ crystalline phases	χ (%)	CaCO ₃ crystalline phases	χ (%)
S15 _{1W1}	5	50	94% C	94±11	100% C	100	100% C	100
		90	7% C	7±3	16% C 5% CCH	21±13	76% C 1% CCH	77±40
		90 [#]	12% C	12±3	63% C 24% CCH	87±3	100% C	100
S15 _{1W2}	5	50	93% C	93±3	100% C	100	100% C	100
		90	3% C	3±1	20% C 12% CCH	32±22	72% C 20% CCH	92±10
		90 [#]	8% C	8±3	80% C 12% CCH	92±3	100% C	100

[#] 15 minutes in ultrasonic bath.